

Resilient Women in Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus* and *Half of a Yellow Sun*

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Abstract

Along with children, women are frequently depicted as the most defenseless victims in war literature worldwide. This image is largely accurate because women are often subjected to lifetime trauma during times of conflict, including molestation, kidnapping, and other forms of brutality. Their pain is exacerbated by the stigma that many communities place on rape, which makes it more difficult for them to reintegrate into society.

This study looks at *Purple Hibiscus* and *Half of a Yellow Sun* by Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie, which portray Nigerian civil war's horrors. Adichie's depiction of women, however, deviates from the typical victim narrative. Her female protagonists refuse to be quiet and exert their agency rather than being passive victims. They fight to survive in the face of death and devastation, standing side by side with men as equals. They frequently even outperform their male counterparts in terms of tenacity and strength.

These women maintain their composure during the most trying times of war, giving others around them courage and hope. They actively contribute to the survival and rehabilitation of the country because of their unflinching resolve and tenacity, which allow them to not only withstand but also overcome adversity. They redefine the role of women in times of conflict by demonstrating their bravery and tenacity, demonstrating that they are not only victims but also sources of strength when faced with hardship.

Keywords: Trauma, civil war, resilience, victims, adversities, endurance.

Introduction

Gender roles have been essentially constant from the beginning of society. Ironically, human women have been systematically suppressed by traditions and practices intended to preserve a strict social framework that is resistant to change, but female animals retain agency over themselves and their libido. Individual rights must inevitably be limited to uphold social order, but women have been disproportionately subjected to this restriction. They are restricted to predetermined domestic roles that haven't changed much despite societal advance-

ments due to centuries of psychological indoctrination. Although the division of labour may help society run, women still do not enjoy full gender equality.

Women and children frequently suffer the most during times of war when human rights are flagrantly violated. Women experience severe trauma from sexual assault, psychological abuse, and domestic exploitation in addition to the physical destruction of war, which is characterized by torture, illness, and death. They still suffer from severe wounds from the conflict, which makes healing a protracted and difficult process. Their anguish goes beyond the battlefield, leaving wounds that persist long after hostilities have ended.

Universality of women's oppression

Despite writing from very different cultural and geographic backgrounds, Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie and Khaled Hosseini both powerfully draw attention to the predicament of women in their own nations. Their works emphasize that violence against women at that time was commonplace. It also highlights how women are still viewed as inferior in a patriarchal society, where the breakdown of law and order during a conflict only makes their plight worse.

The way women are portrayed in Hosseini and Adichie's writings transcends conventional literary representations. Conservative principles do not make these women passive or obedient. They actively participate in the fight for survival as well as the process of rehabilitation, demonstrating their agency even in the face of conflict and devastation. These women are strong, robust, and resolute; they choose to follow the practical routes required for their survival rather than being constrained by antiquated ideas of morality and purity.

When a woman defends herself in these stories, she is defending all women as well. Both before and after the conflict, the women of all ages who are shown in Adichie's and Hosseini's writings are battling to find their position. Each has a unique perspective and survival strategies, and hence a different fate. While some continue to struggle against the limitations that prevent them from achieving their goals, others rise and fly toward them.

Domestic violence and physical abuse

Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus* begins in the midst of a coup. The harsh circumstances in which the protagonists live are revealed in the book, especially during the rule of Eugene, a despotic father who is fixated on maintaining total control over his family. He reacts to challenges to his dominance with vicious violence, particularly directed at the ladies in his life. Life becomes intolerable for both the people of the nation and those living in Eugene's house as the coup intensifies and his authority starts to wane.

Adichie effectively denounces the abuse of women, giving voice to those who will not be helpless victims. The novel emphasizes individuals such as Ifeoma, and Amaka who openly defy social standards and refuse to fit in, even though it mostly centers on Eugene's home and the suffering he causes his family.

Ifeoma courageously takes on the duty of providing for her family during the war after losing her spouse and accepting responsibility for his passing. She resolutely declines assistance from her powerful brother, Eugene, and fights against being persecuted by the authorities when they charge her with disobedient behaviour. Ifeoma remains steadfast in the face of the rioting and turmoil, providing her loved ones with her steadfast support. When she visits Eugene's house, she reveals her troubles with Beatrice in a moving moment, exposing the social and emotional challenges she confronts:

"Look at what this military tyrant is doing to our country... We have not had fuel for three months in Nsukka. I spent the night in the petrol station last week, waiting for fuel. And at the end, the fuel did not come. Some people left their cars in the station because they did not have enough fuel to drive back home... We just called off yet another strike, even though no lecturer has been paid for the last two months. They tell us the Federal Government has no money... Ifukwa, people are leaving the country." (Adichie, 2009a)

Eugene on the other hand struggles to bear the horrors of war. The way he manages his home, from the elegant dinnerware to the evening tea, which is influenced by British traditions, demonstrates his fixation with Christian and colonial ideas. During the coup, Eugene, who owns a newspaper, gives in to pressure. Unable to handle the trauma, Eugene takes his rage and frustration inward and lets it out on his family, especially his wife and daughter, under the oppressive military regime that deprives them of their rights and Tortures them.

Some Western readers may find the family's experiences of severe violence and cruel treatment implausible or perhaps unbelievable. Nonetheless, these un-

pleasant truths are unquestionably accepted by the characters in this book as a part of everyday life. Crimes against women and girls are believed to increase during periods of political unrest or conflict as society becomes preoccupied with more significant, public concerns. In these situations, women suffer considerably more because they are frequently viewed as easy targets who are unlikely to question patriarchal authority. Men are easy candidates for enslavement because of their incapacity to withstand outside influences, which leads them to strike out at those under their authority, especially women.

As a result, the house experiences a reversal of the roles. As Fwangyil points out, "the oppressive and dehumanizing situations women undergo in this novel seem extraordinary, but these are real life stories that have been modified and recreated for the society's awareness. This novel is, in effect, a dramatic indictment of the oppressive attitude of men towards women and children that they are supposed to love and care for. It, therefore, has direct relevance to our contemporary society." (Adichie, 2009b).

Purple Hibiscus is a powerful critique of the patriarchal mindset that permits men to mistreat the people they are meant to love and care for. This criticism strikes a deep chord with modern society. Eugene has been authoritarian all along, sternly upholding his colonial ideals and keeping his family on edge to avoid upsetting him, but things go much worse when the political environment becomes uncertain. His behaviour changes because of the coup, which deals him the first psychological blow. Eugene gets easily upset and reacts violently more often. The family's decision to attend church following the coup is one instance of this shift. Beatrice says she is uncomfortable meeting the priest since she is ill from pregnancy. Already tense, Eugene gets angry. He doesn't confront her then, but when they go home, he brutally beats her, which causes a miscarriage. As recalled by Kambili: "I was in my room after lunch, reading James chapter five because I would talk about the biblical roots of the anointing of the sick during family time, when I heard the sounds. Swift, heavy thuds on my parents' hand carved bed-room door... Mama was slung over his shoulder like the jute sacks of rice... He opened the dining room door... 'There's blood on the floor,' Jaja said. 'I'll get brush from the bathroom'" (Adichie, 2009a).

After Ade Coker's assassination, Eugene viciously beats Kambili, marking the pinnacle of his spiral into insanity. It is believed that the Federal government is responsible for the attack since Eugene publicly criticized the military administration:

Ade Coker was blown up when he opened the package--a package everybody would have

known was from the Head of State even if his wife Yewande had not said that Ade Coker looked at the envelope and said, 'it has the State House seal' before he opened it. (Fwangyil, 2011)

This incident destabilizes Eugene. His mental state worsens when he gets home and discovers Jaja and Kambili clutching a photograph of his deceased father. Eugene cruelly lashes out at Kambili, punishing him severely because he is unable to handle the growing pressure and his loss. Eugene appears to lose all sense of control in the face of turmoil and war, turning to petty excuses to establish his authority and "prove" his manhood by committing heinous acts of violence against his family. As the narrator Kambili movingly relates:

He started to kick me. The metal buckles on his slippers stung like bites from giant mosquitoes. He talked nonstop, out of control, in a mix of Igbo and English, like soft meat and thorny bones. Godlessness. Heathen worship. Hellfire. The kicking increased in tempo and... I curled around myself tighter, around the pieces of painting... Kicking. Kicking. Kicking... More stings. More slaps. A salty wetness warmed my mouth. I closed my eyes and slipped away into quiet. (Adichie, 2009a)

Nigeria provides a setting for the majority of Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's novels, which examine the unstable state of the nation and are frequently based on actual occurrences. This pattern is followed in *Half of a Yellow Sun*, which highlights sufferings Nigerian women endure during the Nigeria-Biafra struggle. Adichie deftly highlights sufferings faced by her people during the war, paying special attention to what happened to women. Her depiction of the anguish women faced as a result of numerous war crimes is both moving and factual.

Adichie challenges the conventional view of women as being morally upright and pure by exposing their hardships in an honest and unapologetic manner. She does not hesitate to depict women who have little choices in such a volatile setting, even if her female characters are strong, tenacious, and dynamic. Regarding her representation in *Half of a Yellow Sun*, Ogwude observes Adichie's sympathetic portrayal of characters, which contrasts with the frequently more constrained portrayals provided by many male authors who have either been unable or

unwilling to do so. There are many strong, diverse, and unrestrained women in the book. The perspective and way of life provided by characters such as Kainene, Olanna, their mother, Auntie Ifeka, Miss Adebayo, and the visiting American professor Edna Whaler is on the lines of Soyinka's portrayal of his women characters, rooted in their culture (Ogwude, 2011).

In Nigeria, women in particular endure unspeakable brutality when war breaks out. Women were murdered in horrifying ways in addition to being raped and kidnapped, and many of these crimes were purposefully concealed. Pregnant women's stomachs were cut open in one of the most heinous crimes, murdering the mother and the unborn child. This agony was justified by the possibility that these infants would turn into rebels in the future. There are innumerable other heartbreaking tales to go along with the commonplace gang rapes in conflict areas and soldiers who would slit pregnant women's bellies at roadblocks while claiming to be looking for rebels hiding in plain sight (Pendergast, 2007).

Conclusion

The female protagonists depicted by Adichie and Hosseini, while experiencing profound adversity, rise as emblems of hope and bravery. These women have an enduring impact on our memories as tenacious individuals who advocate for their rights and combat adversity. Every character exhibits a singular personality and a specific survival strategy, yet all demonstrate an unwavering resilience. Adversity fails to subdue their unyielding determination. Instead of yielding to despair, they provide solace and fortitude, elevating everyone in their vicinity. In the midst of the darkness and destruction of war, these women emerge as symbols of hope, aiding their communities and providing support to others.

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